

18HLT03 SEPTIMET

Metrology to enable rapid and accurate clinical measurements in acute management of sepsis

Deliverable D8

Guidance document describing how rapid near patient (point of care) IVD manufacturers can meet the new IVD EU Regulation 2017/746

Lead partner: LGC

Contributing partners: LNE, METAS, NIB, NPL, PTB, GOSH

Workpackage: 5

Task: 5.5

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This project has received funding from the EMPIR programme co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Summary

Using the input from Tasks 3.1-3.6 and 5.1-5.5, a guidance document on how commercial stakeholders can meet the meet the IVD EU Regulation 2017/746, the replacement for EU Directive 98/79/EC, Regulation (EU) 2017/746, when considering automated, rapid near patient (point of care) testing for sepsis including a description of the metrological support needed to support this process.

This method has been prepared and agreed by the partners LGC, LNE, METAS, NIB, NPL, PTB and reviewed by GOSH.

This deliverable is successfully completed as per Annex 1.

Introduction

The Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament on *in vitro* diagnostic (IVD) medical devices (IVDR) came into effect from 26th May 2022, replacing the Directive 98/79/EC (IVDD). The aim of this update in regulation is to reflect the changes that have developed in the medical devices and IVD sector over the last few years to provide improved safety for EU citizens and protection of public health.

There are significant updates in the Regulation for both manufacturers of medical devices and especially for clinical laboratories in their use of laboratory developed tests (LDT). To clarify *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices, as defined by Regulation (EU) 2017/746 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02017R0746-20220128> are

‘...any medical device which is a reagent, reagent product, calibrator, control material, kit, instrument, apparatus, piece of equipment, software or system, whether used alone or in combination, intended by the manufacturer to be used in vitro for the examination of specimens, including blood and tissue donations, derived from the human body, solely or principally for the purpose of providing information on one or more of the following:

- (a) concerning a physiological or pathological process or state;*
- (b) concerning congenital physical or mental impairments;*
- (c) concerning the predisposition to a medical condition or a disease;*
- (d) to determine the safety and compatibility with potential recipients;*
- (e) to predict treatment response or reactions;*
- (f) to define or monitoring therapeutic measures.*

Some of the key changes brought about by the IVD regulation are the re-classification of medical devices according to risk, the involvement of a notified body to provide conformity assessment for the medical devices and the requirement of a quality management system (QMS) for IVD manufacturers.

Risk Classification for Medical Devices

Most devices under the IVDD were outside of the higher risk category therefore manufacturers could perform self-certification of their CE marked products for placing on the market. However with the new more comprehensive classification under the IVDR this no longer is possible for the majority (~ 80-90 %) of devices. The class groups are determined by the risk they pose to patients and public health (Table 1).

Table 1: The risk classification system of *in vitro* medical devices according to the IVDR.

IVDR Class	Risk	Example Medical Devices
A	Lowest	Buffer solutions and laboratory instruments
B	Low to medium	Self-testing IVD's such as pregnancy tests and cholesterol tests

C	Medium to high	Tests for cancer screening and tests for identification of Infectious disease agents that do not pose a high risk of propagation or transmission
D	Highest	Tests for life threatening transmissible agents or high risk of propagation like HIV tests

The manufacturer's of near patient devices, defined from the IVDR as

".....any device that is not intended for self-testing but is intended to perform testing outside a laboratory environment, generally near to, or at the side of, the patient by a health professional" are required to define the environment in which their test is to be used and perform validation studies in that environment e.g. emergency care rooms, ambulances, doctor's clinics. This specific type of device is a new consideration under the IVDR. The manufacturer must define the intended purpose of their device within the technical documentation and prepare risk management processes which cover the user training and qualifications required for using the device. Within the instructions for use (IFU) document, there should be full instructions for using the device as well as appropriate warnings provided where necessary. The design and specifications of the device should be provided in the technical documentation which is further described.

Notified Bodies

For a device to be placed on the EU market, manufacturers will need to prepare technical documentation which shows evidence of the assessment of the conformity of the device as per the procedures described in the IVDR. Depending on the classification of the device most will require assessment by a Notified Body except for those non-sterile devices classified as Class A. The documentation provided to the Notified Body by the manufacturer must include data on the clinical performance of their device as well as appropriate evidence of implementation of a QMS.

Timelines

The transitional timelines for certain devices to comply with the IVDR were extended on 25th January 2022 (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/112/oj/eng>) to allow for a more progressive roll-out. This change in the application dates means that for certain devices including class C the date of application of the IVDR is 26th May 2026 and for the lowest risk devices (class B and A sterile) this is extended to apply from 26th May 2027. This extension ultimately aims to prevent any shortages of vital healthcare products such as crucial devices for COVID-19 and HIV testing which could come about due to delays in meeting the regulation. This sector has had unprecedented challenges in the recent years due to the global crisis of the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore due to the regulatory changes for devices to meet the IVDR, which now in most situations will require conformity testing, increased involvement of notified bodies is necessary. This is further confounded by the existing shortage of notified bodies so the update in legislation was performed to allow additional time for manufacturers to ensure their devices comply with the performance and safety requirements within the timelines.

The IVDR timeline

The IVDR and Traceability

One of the main aims of the IVDR is to improve the regulation of IVDs by ensuring greater traceability, improving transparency to provide tests that are safer, of higher quality and better design for patients. A metrological framework (reference measurement systems, methods for defining uncertainty etc.) is required to support rapid near patient manufacturers in meeting the IVDR. Reference measurement procedures to support the traceability of these tests are lacking. SEPTIMET has developed reference methods for the analysis of *Staphylococcus aureus* (deliverable 4), a sepsis causing bacteria, using molecular methods and a candidate reference measurement procedure for the quantification of procalcitonin, a protein biomarker for sepsis, in human serum by liquid chromatography/isotope dilution-mass spectrometry (deliverable 2). These reference methods will support industrial stakeholders in the IVD sector by enabling them to develop and calibrate new and existing tests with higher accuracy so that they perform with greater reproducibility and measure the analytes with higher confidence. The updated ISO 17511:2020 (In vitro diagnostic medical devices — Requirements for establishing metrological traceability of values assigned to calibrators, trueness control materials and human samples) standard can make it possible to achieve full metrological traceability for IVDs. In the IVDR metrological traceability is required for devices which are dependent on the use of calibrators and/or control materials, which can be assured through suitable reference measurement procedures or through higher metrological order like a certified reference material if available. Manufacturers must also report within the technical document, required to be submitted for review to the appropriate notified body, the metrological traceability of their test. This must be included in the information supplied with the device, the technical documentation (Annex II) providing information on product verification and validation and in the performance evaluation plan (requirements described in Annex XIII of the IVDR) any available reference measurement procedures or certified reference materials to enable for metrological traceability and the metrological traceability of the device.

Example Technical Documentation

This document contains an example technical documentation including the particular relevant elements from the Annex II and III from the IVDR. The example given in Appendix A is of a hypothetical medical device, '**MRSA detect**', an assay kit for detection and quantification of Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* using digital PCR technology. In Appendix B, an example for the near patient technology, Cepheid® Xpert® test is provided. Please note that for both tests, the technical documentation provided contains information to the best of knowledge of the project. For the Cepheid Xpert test this information has been compiled from the instructions for use (IFU) for the Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test, Ref XPRSARS-COV2-10, 302-3787, Rev B, October 2020, except in sections 3, 5 and 7 by the participating partners in SEPTIMET. NOTE: These documents have not been completed by the manufacturers. Appendix C contains examples of how to fulfil analytical performance categories from relevant literature.

In addition to the technical documentation provided there is a requirement to provide post market surveillance (REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex III). After transfer of a test into routine use, the assay should be implemented into the laboratory's quality management system. Assay performance should be assessed regularly using internal and external quality control. Conditions requiring revalidation should be defined. Revalidation is required after a change of performance specification, and for regulatory body approved assays performed with modifications. General guidance for verification and validation of nucleic acid amplification-based examination procedures can be found in ISO 17822:2020. Further specific guidance for methods detecting SARS-CoV-2 by nucleic acid amplification methods can be found in ISO/TS 5798:2022.

Appendix A: Example technical documentation for digital PCR test to quantify MRSA in a sample

Technical Documentation

1. Device description and specification, including variants and accessories (Regulation (EU) 2017/746, Annex II, Section 1)

No.	Field	Information
1.1	Product or trade name	MRSA detect
1.2	Basic unique device identifier	Catalogue number NNPM100
1.3	Intended purpose, intended user and general device description	MRSA detect is a probe based digital PCR kit for determination of the presence and quantity (copy number concentration) of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> and Methicillin-resistant <i>S. aureus</i> (MRSA). The manual test requires genomic DNA (gDNA) as input. MRSA detect is to be performed by laboratory professionals using the QX200 digital PCR system (Bio-rad) and QuantaSoft software, version 1.7, Regulatory edition.
1.4	Qualification of the product as a device	MRSA detect is a kit when used in combination with appropriate consumables, apparatus, instrument and software for <i>in vitro</i> use for the examination of gDNA from specimens derived from the human body to give information about presence of a pathogen and associated drug resistance.
1.5	Classification / risk class of the device	Class C As per rule 3 of Regulation (EU) 2017/746, MRSA detect is intended for the detection of the presence of an infectious agent without a high risk of propagation.
1.6	Configurations and variants of the device	N/A
1.7	Composition of the device	The kit contains: 100 tests of MRSA detect Each test contains three tubes: Duplex: Primer pairs and probes for amplification and detection of each target

		<p>Once added to the reaction mix, the concentrations of each component above are 900 nM for each primer and 200 nM for each probe. The labelled used for probe detection is FAM and HEX in duplex.</p> <p>PC: Positive control for all targets consisting of gDNA of MRSA</p> <p>NC: Negative control for all targets consisting of nuclease free water</p>
1.8	Principle of action	<p>Extracted DNA is amplified using sets of specific primers (forward and reverse) and probe(s) in the polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Before the start of DNA amplification, reaction mixture is divided into partitions.</p> <p>Amplification of the target sequence is carried out <i>in vitro</i> by thermostable DNA polymerase in the presence of oligonucleotide primers, probe and deoxynucleotide triphosphates (dNTPs) in a defined reaction buffer. The PCR products are monitored by fluorimetry at the end of the PCR using a fluorescent probe. The probe anneals to the target sequence between both selected oligonucleotide primers. In the next stage DNA polymerase is activated. Amplification is cyclic and consists of two steps: (1) DNA heat denaturation to a single-stranded DNA and (2) specific annealing of primers and a probe to the target sequence and DNA synthesis based on the oligonucleotides bound to both strands of DNA, by DNA polymerase at suitable temperature. During the polymerisation, DNA polymerase with its exonuclease activity degrades the probe and allows the separation of the fluorescent reporter from the quencher leading to emission of fluorescence by the reporter.</p> <p>After DNA amplification by PCR the partitions are counted and the amplitude of the fluorescence of each partition is measured. As the partitions contain either one or more target sequences or are empty, they are divided into positive partitions (positive fluorescent data) and negative partitions (negative fluorescent data), based on a threshold. The number of positive partitions and the number of all accepted partitions are the basis for</p>

		calculation of absolute copy number of the target sequence in in the DNA preparation.
1.9	Accessories and device combinations	N/A
1.10	Accessories / equipment required for use but not provided with the devices	<p>This kit is to be used with:</p> <p>QX200™ Droplet Generator (Cat #186-4002)</p> <p>QX200 Droplet Reader (Cat #186-4003)</p> <p>C1000 Touch™ Thermal Cycler with 96–Deep Well Reaction Module (Cat #185-1197)</p> <p>PX1™ PCR Plate Sealer (Cat #181-4000)</p> <p>ddPCR™ Supermix for Probes (No dUTP) (Cat #1863024)</p> <p>QuantaSoft software, version 1.7, Regulatory edition (Cat #1864011)</p>
1.11	Reference to previous and similar Generations of the Device	N/A

2. Information supplied by the manufacturer (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 2)

Label

MRSA detect Catalogue number NNPM100

In vitro diagnostic device

For QX200 dPCR system (Bio-rad)

100 tests/kit

Store at -20 °C or below

Shelf life 12 months after manufacturing

Instructions for use

1.1. Preparation of the reaction mixture (QX200)

Before preparation of the reaction mix, turn on the PCR apparatus.

The reaction mixture is prepared in the PCR UV cabinet in the laboratory for PCR reaction mixture preparation, as described:

- Prepare a properly orientated 96-wells microtiter plate or properly numbered 8-well strips with covers.

- Prepare a 1.5 or a 2 mL microtubes for the reaction mix. Thaw probe and primers completely at room temperature and mix thoroughly before use. Exposure to light should be minimized.
- Pipette the adequate quantity of dedicated ddPCR Supermix, primers and probe in this order in the microtube (see table below for quantities). Always mix and briefly centrifuge solutions before adding to reaction mix.

Component	Final	Volume for 1 reaction (µL)	Volume for 1 reaction (µL) with 20% surplus
2x ddPCR Supermix	1x	10	12
duplex	900/900/200 nM	6	7.2

- Typically, individual reactions containing both PCR mastermix and sample template are prepared to include a 10 % excess (total volume 22 µL/reaction) to allow for pipetting 20 µL into the DG8 cartridge. In order to achieve 10 % excess of reaction mix, it is recommended to prepare 120 % of reaction mix, then pipette 17.6 µL of reaction mixture (10% surplus) in each selected well of the 96-well plate or 8-well strips before adding DNA.

1.2. Adding of DNA and droplet preparation (QX200)

The 96-wells microtiter plate or 8-well strips with mastermix are carried from the PCR UV cabinet in laboratory for PCR reaction mixture preparation to the PCR UV cabinet in laboratory for adding DNA.

DNA is added following these steps:

- In selected wells of 96-wells microtiter plate or 8-well strip, add 4.4 µL sample DNA. Always start by adding water for first NTC, continue in recommended order with positive control, sample DNA and other controls. Always finish with water for the last NTC.
- The 96-wells microtiter plate is sealed with the pierceable foil, 8-well strip with covers.
- The 96-wells microtiter plate or 8-well strip is mixed and centrifuged to ensure the reaction mix and the DNA are collected at the bottom of the wells.
- 20 µL of the reaction mixture is transferred to the cartridge for droplet generation.
- Droplets (40 µL) are transferred from cartridge in to a new 96-well plate, according to the predefined plate setup.
- The plate is sealed with the pierceable foil.
- Start the amplification step not longer than 30 minutes after sealing the plate.

1.3. DNA amplification and fluorescent measurement (QX200)

The 96-well plate is placed in the PCR cycler and the following PCR programme is run:

Cycles	Time	Temperature (°C)
1	10 min	95

40	30 sec	94
	60 sec	60
1	10 min	98
1	infinite	4

Lid temperature: 105°C

Volume: 40µL

1.4. Reading of the droplets (QX200)

After PCR the 96-well microtiter plate is transferred to the droplet reader. Before the reading is engaged, the parameters of droplet reading need to be set in the QuantaSoft software.

2. DATA ANALYSIS

2.1. Primary analysis of dPCR results (QX100/200)

Primary analysis is made in the QuantaSoft software and all additional data analysis is done in an Excel worksheet in 'Microsoft Excel Workbook' format.

Primary analysis in the QuantaSoft software consists of visual checking of all results (fluorescence of negative and positive droplets in samples and controls, any unexpected deviations) and setting of the fluorescence amplitude threshold. The threshold is set above the cluster of negative droplets based on the amplitude of positive and negative control samples. With this step, the number of positive droplets is determined. After the primary analysis the results are exported to the Excel.

3. RESULT INTERPRETATION

In the data interpretation first the results of controls are inspected for compliance. If all quality controls are in accordance with the acceptance criteria, the data from samples are checked. The following parameters and criteria need to be taken in account:

- If the number of accepted partitions is < 10 000 for QX200 the reaction should be discarded.
- dPCR reaction is positive if there are at least 3 positive partitions.
- NTC: Both NTCs for all assays have to be negative, otherwise the chance of reaction mix contamination (first NTC) or transfer of DNA to another well (second NTC) should be considered. If any NTC is positive, dPCR should be repeated.
- Positive control: DNA material containing target sequence with a known target copy number concentration should be positive, otherwise an error during dPCR reaction or setup should be considered. Results should not differ from the known value for more than 25%.
- Sample is considered positive when both technical repeats are positive (copies/reaction is above LOD of the method).
- When both replicates are negative, it is considered that the target is not detected in the sample.
- dPCR is ambiguous when the result of one technical repeat is positive while the second repeat is negative. In that case, it is necessary to repeat the analysis with increased

quantity of DNA or replicates, if possible. If the result is still ambiguous, the DNA extraction should be repeated, unless the result is near LOD.

- The result is reported as follows:

Target 1 (FAM)	Target 2 (HEX)	Result	Note
Positive	Positive	MRSA positive	
Negative	Positive	MRSA negative	MSSA detected
Negative	Negative	MRSA negative	MSSA not detected
Positive	Negative	mecA detected	Methicillin resistance detected but <i>S. aureus</i> not detected

MSSA: methicillin sensitive *S. aureus*

MRSA: methicillin resistant *S. aureus*

mecA: the gene indicating methicillin resistance

3. Design and manufacturing information (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 3)

No.	Field	Information
3.1	Design Information	MRSA detect uses two targets, one of which indicates presence of <i>S. aureus</i> and the other indicates methicillin resistance. The assay sequences are previously described (O'Sullivan et. al DOI 10.3390/ijms151121476).
3.2	Manufacturing Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oligonucleotides synthesis and purification by third party supplier (appropriate certificate attached) QC of oligonucleotides Dilution of oligonucleotides to 100 nM starting concentrations Preparation of batches of target 1 and 2 assays (containing forward and reverse primers and labelled probes) QC of batches

4. General Safety and Performance Requirements (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 4)

This section must fulfill all applicable General Safety and Performance Requirements. Please see further detail provided in appendix B.

5. Benefit-Risk Analysis and Risk Management (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 5)

This section contains the risk management files, at minimum to provide the risk management plan and report. Please see further detail provided in appendix B.

6. Benefit-Risk Analysis and Risk Management (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6)

This section provides information on some of the fields as an example, however some pieces of information are left blank, fields filled in grey. Please see further detail provided in appendix B for some of the fields.

No.	Field	Information
6.1	Specimen Type / Handling	Extracted DNA from commercial kits can be analysed using MRSA detect .
6.2	Analytical Performance	<p>Analytical Sensitivity (Limit of Detection)</p> <p>To measure the LOD for MRSA, a 10x dilutions series of MRSA positive control material were prepared using nuclease free water and a negative template control (NTC) that contain ddH₂O water instead of sample. The verified values from dPCR were used to calculate the assigned copy number concentration of the targets for the dilution series.</p> <p>In dPCR, for low sample concentration, the statistical distribution in the repeat measurements is not Gaussian but discrete. Therefore, it is not possible to derive the LOD from the standard deviation of repeat measurements. In the absence of a blank value (BV), the theoretical LOD for dPCR can be calculated from counting statistics assuming Poisson distribution. Therefore, the LOD concentration for DNA in the sample material is calculated using the equation 1</p> $C_{LOD} = \frac{-\ln 0.05}{N_{tot} V_d D} \quad (1)$ <p>Where N_{tot} is the number of accepted droplets and V_d is the droplet size. In Equation (1) the LOD is corrected by the dilution factor D that results from concentration changes introduced by addition of reagents. Further details for LOD and LOQ are previously shown (Falak et al., 2021).</p> <p>The observed concentration calculated from the average from all replicate measurements followed the expected concentration down to ~ 220 copies per mL for the MRSA reference method.</p> <p>The limit for LOQ is given by counting statistics and can be calculated using the formula shown previously (Falak et al., 2021) and below in Equation 2</p> $C_{LOQ} = \frac{1}{R^2 N_{tot} V_d D} \quad (2)$

		<p>The Equation (2) can be used to calculate the LOQ. For the MRSA the estimated $C_{LOQ} = 376$ copies per mL. In general, the LOQ can also be improved by averaging replicate measurements.</p> <p>LOD is 222 copies/mL.</p> <p>LOQ is 376 copies/mL.</p> <p>Precision</p> <p>The variability of the method, described as a % coefficient of variation representing the repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility is reported below using the assessment of two EQA schemes (INSTAND e.V. EQA Group 539: Bacterial genome detection MRSA or cMRSA (community acquired MRSA) May and November 2022; Samples 2215391-4 from the May inter-laboratory study and samples 2225391, 2225393 and 2225394 from the November inter-laboratory study, PC indicates positive control which is a genomic DNA material). Droplet volume variability for QX100/200 is previously described (Bogožalec Košir et al., 2017). . In each scheme the materials were analysed by three external laboratories; NML at LGC, PTB and NIB.</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Sample</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Pooled mean (copies/μL)</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Reproducibility CV (%)</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Intermediate precision CV (%)</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Repeatability CV (%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>2215391</td><td>431</td><td>16.39</td><td>14.27</td><td>3.82</td></tr> <tr><td>2215392</td><td>826</td><td>15.75</td><td>6.22</td><td>3.11</td></tr> <tr><td>2215393</td><td>1302</td><td>9.91</td><td>8.7</td><td>2.33</td></tr> <tr><td>2215394</td><td>8227</td><td>12.08</td><td>11.94</td><td>4.39</td></tr> <tr><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td><td> </td></tr> <tr><td>2225391</td><td>1018</td><td>12.17</td><td>11.22</td><td>4.27</td></tr> <tr><td>2225393</td><td>122</td><td>12.02</td><td>8.58</td><td>6.23</td></tr> <tr><td>2225394</td><td>491</td><td>25.9</td><td>17.33</td><td>4.58</td></tr> <tr style="border-bottom: 1px solid black;"><td>PC</td><td>1115</td><td>12.62</td><td>7.52</td><td>5.72</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p>PC: positive control</p> <p>Copies per mL of primary sample with standard (u_r) and expanded uncertainty (U_r) expressed as a %, with two degrees of freedom ($k=4.3$ 95% confidence interval):</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Assay</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Sample</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">Estimate (copies/mL)</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">u_r(%)</th> <th style="border-top: 1px solid black; border-bottom: 1px solid black;">U_r(%)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>coA</td><td>2215391</td><td>1.32E+05</td><td>8.19</td><td>35.2</td></tr> <tr><td>mecA</td><td>2215391</td><td>1.48E+05</td><td>7.29</td><td>31.35</td></tr> <tr><td>Sa442</td><td>2215391</td><td>1.56E+05</td><td>6.95</td><td>29.88</td></tr> <tr><td>coA</td><td>2215392</td><td>2.67E+05</td><td>8.96</td><td>38.51</td></tr> <tr><td>Sa442</td><td>2215392</td><td>2.86E+05</td><td>8.37</td><td>35.97</td></tr> <tr style="border-bottom: 1px solid black;"><td>mecA</td><td>2215393</td><td>4.31E+05</td><td>4.28</td><td>18.41</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Sample	Pooled mean (copies/ μ L)	Reproducibility CV (%)	Intermediate precision CV (%)	Repeatability CV (%)	2215391	431	16.39	14.27	3.82	2215392	826	15.75	6.22	3.11	2215393	1302	9.91	8.7	2.33	2215394	8227	12.08	11.94	4.39						2225391	1018	12.17	11.22	4.27	2225393	122	12.02	8.58	6.23	2225394	491	25.9	17.33	4.58	PC	1115	12.62	7.52	5.72	Assay	Sample	Estimate (copies/mL)	u_r (%)	U_r (%)	coA	2215391	1.32E+05	8.19	35.2	mecA	2215391	1.48E+05	7.29	31.35	Sa442	2215391	1.56E+05	6.95	29.88	coA	2215392	2.67E+05	8.96	38.51	Sa442	2215392	2.86E+05	8.37	35.97	mecA	2215393	4.31E+05	4.28	18.41
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		mecA	2225391	4.40E+05	4.03	17.34
		Sa442	2225391	3.19E+05	5.57	23.94
		coA	2225393	3.02E+04	7.34	31.57
		mecA	2225393	5.27E+04	4.27	18.35
		Sa442	2225393	5.42E+04	4.16	17.87
		coA	2225394	1.54E+05	13.61	58.53
		mecA	2225394	1.71E+05	12.3	52.9
		Sa442	2225394	1.82E+05	11.57	49.77
6.3	Clinical Performance					
6.4	Performance of self-testing devices / Near-patient testing devices					
6.5	Scientific Validity					
6.6	Performance Evaluation Report					
6.7	Stability (REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.3)					
6.8	Software Verification and Validation / Functional Safety / Cybersecurity (REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.4)					
6.9	CHEMICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES					

	(REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.5)	
6.9.1	Nanoparticle Technology	
6.9.2	Hazardous Substances	
6.9.3	Substances of Animal / Human / Microbiological Origin	
6.9.4	Sterile Devices or Devices with Defined Microbiological Condition	
6.9.5	Constructional Safety	
6.9.5.1	Mechanical Safety	
6.9.5.2	Electrical safety / electromagnetic compatibility	
6.9.5.3	Ionising and non-ionising radiation	
6.9.5.4	Environmental protection and safe disposal	
6.9.5.5	Packaging	
6.9.5.6	Devices with connection to other device(s)	
6.9.6	Devices with a Measuring Function	

7. Summary of Safety and Performance (SSP) (only class C and D devices) (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Article 29)

Note: This section to include information such as name of device, use, description, performance evaluation, reference to harmonised standards, suggestions as to training required for users, any warnings and precautions about its use.

Appendix B: Example technical documentation for near patient test

Technical Documentation

1. Device description and specification, including variants and accessories (Regulation (EU) 2017/746, Annex II, Section 1)

No.	Field	Information
1.1	Product or trade name	Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2
1.2	Basic unique device identifier	Catalog #: XPRSARS-COV2-10
1.3	Intended purpose, intended user and general device description	<p>The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test is a real-time RT-PCR test intended for the qualitative detection of nucleic acid from the SARS-CoV-2 in nasopharyngeal swab, nasal swab, or nasal wash/aspirate specimen collected from individuals who are suspected of COVID-19 infection.</p> <p>Results are for the identification of SARS-CoV-2 RNA. Positive results are indicative of the presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA; clinical correlation with patient history and other diagnostic information is necessary to determine patient infection status. Positive results do not rule out bacterial infection or co-infection with other viruses. The agent detected may not be the definite cause of disease.</p> <p>Negative results do not preclude SARS-CoV-2 infection and should not be used as the sole basis for treatment or other patient management decisions. Negative results must be combined with clinical observations, patient history, and epidemiological information.</p> <p>The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test is intended to be performed by trained users in both laboratory and near patient testing settings.</p>
1.4	Qualification of the product as a device	Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2 is a kit when used in combination with appropriate consumables, apparatus, instrument and software for <i>in vitro</i> use for the examination of gDNA from specimens derived from the human body to give information about presence of a pathogen.
1.5	Classification / risk class of the device	Class C

1.6	Configurations and variants of the device	N/A																						
1.7	Composition of the device	<p>The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 kit contains sufficient reagents to process 10 specimens or quality control samples.</p> <p>The kit contains the following:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="740 495 1385 1182"> <tr> <td>Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Cartridges with Integrated Reaction Tubes</td> <td>10</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Bead 1, Bead 2, and Bead 3 (freeze-dried)</td> <td>1 of each per cartridge</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Lysis Reagent</td> <td>1.5 mL per cartridge</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Binding Reagent</td> <td>1.5 mL per cartridge</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Elution Reagent</td> <td>3.0 mL per cartridge</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Disposable Transfer Pipettes</td> <td>10-12 per kit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CD</td> <td>1 per kit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Assay Definition File (ADF)</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Instructions to import ADF into GeneXpert software</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Flyer</td> <td>1 per kit</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Directions to locate the Product Insert on www.cepheid.com</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Cartridges with Integrated Reaction Tubes	10	Bead 1, Bead 2, and Bead 3 (freeze-dried)	1 of each per cartridge	Lysis Reagent	1.5 mL per cartridge	Binding Reagent	1.5 mL per cartridge	Elution Reagent	3.0 mL per cartridge	Disposable Transfer Pipettes	10-12 per kit	CD	1 per kit	Assay Definition File (ADF)		Instructions to import ADF into GeneXpert software		Flyer	1 per kit	Directions to locate the Product Insert on www.cepheid.com	
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Instructions to import ADF into GeneXpert software																								
Flyer	1 per kit																							
Directions to locate the Product Insert on www.cepheid.com																								
1.8	Principle of action	<p>The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test is an automated in vitro diagnostic test for qualitative detection of nucleic acid from SARS-CoV-2. The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test is performed on GeneXpert Instrument Systems.</p> <p>The GeneXpert Instrument Systems automate and integrate sample preparation, nucleic acid extraction and amplification, and detection of the target sequences in simple or complex samples using real-time PCR assays. The systems consist of an instrument, computer, and preloaded software for running tests and viewing the results. The systems require the use of single use disposable cartridges that hold the RT-PCR reagents and host the RT-PCR process. Because the cartridges are self contained, cross-contamination between samples is minimized. For a full description of the systems, see the <i>GeneXpert Dx System Operator Manual</i> or the <i>GeneXpert Infinity System Operator Manual</i>.</p> <p>The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test includes reagents for the detection of RNA from SARS-CoV-2 in NP swab, nasal swab, or nasal wash/aspirate specimen. A Sample Processing</p>																						

		<p>Control (SPC) and a Probe Check Control (PCC) are also included in the cartridge utilized by the GeneXpert instrument. The SPC is present to control for adequate processing of the sample and to monitor for the presence of potential inhibitor(s) in the RT-PCR reaction. The SPC also ensures that the RT-PCR reaction conditions (temperature and time) are appropriate for the amplification reaction and that the RT-PCR reagents are functional. The PCC verifies reagent rehydration, PCR tube filling, and confirms that all reaction components are present in the cartridge including monitoring for probe integrity and dye stability.</p> <p>The NP swab, nasal swab, or nasal wash/aspirate specimen is collected and placed into a transport tube containing 3 mL of viral transport medium or 3 mL of saline. The specimen is briefly mixed by rapidly inverting the collection tube 5 times. Using the supplied transfer pipette, the sample is transferred to the sample chamber of the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge. The GeneXpert cartridge is loaded onto the GeneXpert Instrument System platform, which performs hands-off, automated sample processing, and real-time RT-PCR for detection of viral RNA.</p>
1.9	Accessories and device combinations	<p>GeneXpert Dx or GeneXpert Infinity systems</p> <p>GX-II - 2 module instrument with desktop computer Catalog #: GXII-2-D</p> <p>GX-II - 2 module instrument with laptop computer Catalog #: GXII-2-L</p> <p>GX-IV - 4 module instrument with desktop computer Catalog #: GXIV-4-D</p> <p>GX-IV - 4 module instrument with laptop computer Catalog #: GXIV-4-L</p> <p>GX-XVI - 16 module instrument with desktop computer Catalog #: GXXVI-16-D</p> <p>GX-XVI - 16 module instrument with laptop computer Catalog #: GXXVI-16-L</p> <p>GeneXpert Infinity 48s Catalog #: Infinity-48</p> <p>GeneXpert Infinity 80 Catalog #: Infinity-80</p>
1.10	Accessories / equipment required for use but not provided with the devices	<p>Materials Required but Not Provided</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nylon flocked swab (Copan P/N 502CS01, 503CS01) or equivalent

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viral transport medium, 3 mL (Copan P/N 330C) or equivalent • 0.85% (w/v) saline, 3 mL • Sample Collection Kit for Viruses (Cepheid P/N SWAB/B-100, SWAB/M-100, SWAB/F-100) or equivalent • GeneXpert Dx or GeneXpert Infinity systems (catalog number varies by configuration): GeneXpert instrument, computer, barcode scanner, operator manual. <p>For GeneXpert Dx System: GeneXpert Dx software version 4.7b or higher</p> <p>For GeneXpert Infinity-80 and Infinity-48s systems: Xpertise software version 6.4b or higher</p>
1.11	Reference to previous and similar Generations of the Device	N/A

1. Information supplied by the manufacturer (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 2)

Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Labels Catalog # XPRSARS-COV2-10

Cartridge Label
 Label P/N 302-3550, Rev A

Kit Label
 Label P/N 302-3554, Rev A

Hazard Warning Label
 Label P/N 301-6687, Rev A

Cartridge Label P/N 302-3555, Rev A

Box Label
 Label P/N 302-3556, Rev A

CD Label
 Label P/N 302-3561, Rev A

7. Storage and Handling

- Store the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridges at 2-28°C.
- Do not open a cartridge lid until you are ready to perform testing.
- Do not use a cartridge that is wet or has leaked.

Note: Safety Data Sheets (SDS) are available at www.cepheidinternational.com under the SUPPORT tab.

10 Warnings and Precautions

10.1 General

- For in vitro diagnostic use.
- Positive results are indicative of presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA.
- Report all positive results to the appropriate health authorities as required.
- Treat all biological specimens, including used cartridges, as if capable of transmitting infectious agents. Because it is often impossible to know which might be infectious, all biological specimens should be handled using standard precautions. Guidelines for specimen handling are available from the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.
- Follow safety procedures set by your institution for working with chemicals and handling biological specimens.
- Consult your institution's environmental waste personnel on proper disposal of used cartridges, which may contain amplified material. This material may exhibit characteristics of federal EPA Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) hazardous waste requiring specific disposal requirements. Check state and local regulations as they may differ from federal disposal regulations. Institutions should check the hazardous waste disposal requirements within their respective countries.

10.2 Specimens

- Maintain proper storage conditions during specimen transport to ensure the integrity of the specimen (see Section 12, Specimen Collection, Transport, and Storage). Specimen stability under shipping conditions other than those recommended has not been evaluated.

10.3 Assay/Reagent

- Do not open the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge lid except when adding specimen.
- Do not use a cartridge that has been dropped after removing it from the packaging.
- Do not shake the cartridge. Shaking or dropping the cartridge after opening the cartridge lid may yield non-determinate results.
- Do not place the sample ID label on the cartridge lid or on the barcode label on the cartridge.
- Do not use a cartridge with a damaged barcode label.
- Do not use a cartridge that has a damaged reaction tube.
- Each single-use Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge is used to process one test. Do not reuse processed cartridges.
- Each single-use disposable pipette is used to transfer one specimen. Do not reuse disposable pipettes
- Do not use a cartridge if it appears wet or if the lid seal appears to have been broken.
- Wear clean lab coats and gloves. Change gloves between the handling of each specimen.
- In the event of a spill of specimens or controls, wear gloves and absorb the spill with paper towels. Then, thoroughly clean the contaminated area with a 10% freshly prepared household chlorine bleach. Allow a minimum of two minutes of contact time. Ensure the work area is dry before using 70% denatured ethanol to remove bleach residue. Allow surface to dry completely before proceeding. Or, follow your institution's standard procedures for a contamination or spill event. For equipment, follow the manufacturer's recommendations for decontamination of equipment.
- Biological specimens, transfer devices, and used cartridges should be considered capable of transmitting infectious agents requiring standard precautions. Follow your institution's

environmental waste procedures for proper disposal of used cartridges and unused reagents. These materials may exhibit characteristics of chemical hazardous waste requiring specific disposal. If country or regional regulations do not provide clear direction on proper disposal, biological specimens and used cartridges should be disposed per WHO [World Health Organization] medical waste handling and disposal guidelines.

11 Chemical Hazards

- Signal Word: WARNING
- UN GHS Hazard Statements
 - Harmful if swallowed.
 - May be harmful in contact with skin.
 - Causes eye irritation.
- UN GHS Precautionary Statements
 - Prevention
 - Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - Response
 - Call a POISON CENTER or doctor/physician if you feel unwell.
 - If skin irritation occurs: Get medical advice/attention.
 - IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.

12. Specimen Collection, Transport, and Storage

Proper specimen collection, storage, and transport are critical to the performance of this test. Inadequate specimen collection, improper specimen handling and/or transport may yield a false result. See Section 12.1 for nasopharyngeal swab collection procedure, Section 12.2 for nasal swab collection procedure, and Section 12.3 for nasal wash/aspirate collection procedure. Nasopharyngeal swab, nasal swab and nasal wash/aspirate specimens can be stored in viral transport medium or saline, at room temperature (15-30 °C) for up to 8 hours and refrigerated (2-8 °C) up to 7 days until testing is performed on the GeneXpert Instrument Systems.

Refer to the WHO Laboratory Biosafety Guidance Related to the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19). [https://www.who.int/publications-detail/laboratory-biosafety-guidance-related-to-coronavirus-disease-2019-\(covid-19\)](https://www.who.int/publications-detail/laboratory-biosafety-guidance-related-to-coronavirus-disease-2019-(covid-19))

12.1 Nasopharyngeal Swab Collection Procedure

Insert the swab into either nostril, passing it into the posterior nasopharynx (see Figure 1). Rotate swab by firmly brushing against the nasopharynx several times. Remove and place the swab into the tube containing 3mL of viral transport medium or 3mL of saline. Break swab at the indicated break line and cap the specimen collection tube tightly.

Figure 1. Nasopharyngeal Swab Collection

12.2 Nasal Swab Collection Procedure

1. Insert a nasal swab 1 to 1.5 cm into a nostril. Rotate the swab against the inside of the nostril for 3 seconds while applying pressure with a finger to the outside of the nostril (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Nasal Swab Collection for First Nostril

2. Repeat on the other nostril with the same swab, using external pressure on the outside of the other nostril (see Figure 3). To avoid specimen contamination, do not touch the swab tip to anything other than the inside of the nostril.

Figure 3. Nasal Swab Collection for Second Nostril

3. Remove and place the swab into the tube containing 3 mL of viral transport medium or 3 mL of saline. Break swab at the indicated break line and cap the specimen collection tube tightly.

12.3 Nasal Wash/Aspirate Collection Procedure

1. Nasal wash/aspirate specimens can be collected following the user institution standard procedure. Also, refer to the WHO guidelines for the collection of human nasal wash/aspirate specimens.

https://www.who.int/influenza/human_animal_interface/virology_laboratories_and_vaccines/guidelines_collection_h5n1_humans/en/

2. Using a transfer pipette, transfer 600 µL of the undiluted nasal wash/aspirate specimen into the tube containing 3 mL of viral transport medium or 3 mL of saline and then cap the tube.

13 Procedure

Start the test within 30 minutes of adding the sample to the cartridge.

13.1 Preparing the Cartridge

1. Remove a cartridge from the package.
2. Check the specimen transport tube is closed.
3. Mix specimen by rapidly inverting the specimen transport tube 5 times. Open cap on the specimen transport tube.
4. Open the cartridge lid.
5. Remove the transfer pipette from the wrapper.
6. Squeeze the top bulb of the transfer pipette completely and then place the pipette tip in the specimen transport tube (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Transfer Pipette

7. Release the top bulb of the pipette to fill the pipette before removing from the tube. After filling pipette, excess sample will be seen in the overflow reservoir bulb of the pipette (see Figure 4). Check that the pipette does not contain bubbles.

8. To transfer the sample to the cartridge, squeeze the top bulb of the transfer pipette completely again to empty the contents of the pipette (300 µL) into the large opening (Sample Chamber) in the cartridge shown in Figure 5. Dispose of the used pipette.

Figure 5. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Cartridge (Top View)

9. Close the cartridge lid. Note: Take care to dispense the entire volume of liquid into the Sample Chamber. False negative results may occur if insufficient sample is added to the cartridge.

13.2 External Controls

External controls such as SeraCare AccuPlex™ Reference Material Kit, catalog number 0505-0126 (Order Code CEPHEID) are available but not provided and may be used in accordance with local, state, and federal accrediting organizations, as applicable.

To run a control using the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test, perform the following steps:

1. Mix control by rapidly inverting the external control tube 5 times. Open cap on external control tube.
2. Open the cartridge lid.
3. Using a clean transfer pipette, transfer one draw of the external control sample (300 µL) into the large opening (Sample Chamber) in the cartridge shown in Figure 5.
4. Close cartridge lid.

13.3 Starting the Test

Note Before you start the test, make sure that the system contains modules with GeneXpert Dx software version 4.7b or higher or Infinity Xpertise software 6.4b or higher, and that the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Assay Definition File is imported into the software. This section lists the default steps to operate the GeneXpert Instrument System. For detailed instructions, see the GeneXpert Dx System Operator Manual or the GeneXpert Infinity System Operator Manual, depending on the model that is being used.

1. Turn on the GeneXpert Instrument System:

- GeneXpert Dx:

If using the GeneXpert Dx instrument, first turn on the instrument and then turn on the computer. Log into the Windows operating system. The GeneXpert software may launch automatically or may require double-clicking on the GeneXpert Dx shortcut icon on the Windows® desktop.

or

- GeneXpert Infinity System:

If using the GeneXpert Infinity instrument, power up the instrument by turning the power switch clockwise to the ON position. On the Windows desktop, double-click the Xpertise Software shortcut icon to launch the software.

2. Log on to the System software. The login screen appears. Type your user name and password.
3. In the GeneXpert System window, click Create Test (GeneXpert Dx) or Orders followed by Order Test (Infinity).
4. Scan or type in the Patient ID (optional). If typing the Patient ID, make sure the Patient ID is typed correctly. The Patient ID is shown on the left side of the View Results window and is associated with the test result.
5. Scan or type in the Sample ID. If typing the Sample ID, make sure the Sample ID is typed correctly. The Sample ID is shown on the left side of the View Results window and is associated with the test result.
6. Scan the barcode on the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge. Using the barcode information, the software automatically fills the boxes for the following fields: Reagent Lot ID, Cartridge SN, Expiration Date and Selected Assay.

Note: If the barcode on the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge does not scan, then repeat the test with a new cartridge.

7. Click Start Test (GeneXpert Dx) or Submit (Infinity) if Auto-Submit is not enabled. In the dialog box that appears, type your password, if required.

For the GeneXpert Dx Instrument

A. Locate the module with the blinking green light, open the instrument module door and load the cartridge.

B. Close the door. The test starts and the green light stops blinking. When the test is finished, the light turns off and the door will unlock. Remove the cartridge.

C. Dispose of used cartridges in the appropriate sample waste containers according to your institution's standard practices.

or

For the GeneXpert Infinity System

A. After clicking Submit, you will be asked to place the cartridge on the conveyor belt. After placing the cartridge, click OK to continue. The cartridge will be automatically loaded, the test will run and the used cartridge will be placed onto the waste shelf for disposal.

B. When all samples are loaded, click on the End Order Test icon.

Note: Do not turn off or unplug the instruments while a test is in progress. Turning off or unplugging the GeneXpert instrument or computer will stop the test.

14 Viewing and Printing Results

For detailed instructions on how to view and print the results, see the GeneXpert Dx System Operator Manual or the GeneXpert Infinity System Operator Manual.

15 Quality Control

15.1 Internal Controls

Each cartridge includes a Sample Processing Control (SPC) and Probe Check Control (PCC).

Sample Processing Control (SPC) - Ensures that the sample was processed correctly. The SPC verifies that sample processing is adequate. Additionally, this control detects sample-associated inhibition of the real-time PCR assay, ensures that the PCR reaction conditions (temperature and time) are appropriate for the amplification reaction, and that the PCR reagents are functional. The SPC should be positive in a negative sample and can be negative or positive in a positive sample. The SPC passes if it meets the validated acceptance criteria.

Probe Check Control (PCC) - Before the start of the PCR reaction, the GeneXpert System measures the fluorescence signal from the probes to monitor bead rehydration, reaction tube filling, probe integrity, and dye stability. The PCC passes if it meets the validated acceptance criteria.

15.2 External Controls

External controls should be used in accordance with local, state, and federal accrediting organizations as applicable.

16. Interpretation of Results

The results are interpreted automatically by the GeneXpert System and are clearly shown in the View Results window. The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test provides test results based on the detection of two gene targets according to the algorithms shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Possible Results

Result Text	N2	E	SPC
SARS-CoV-2 POSITIVE	+	+/-	+/-
SARS-CoV-2 PRESUMPTIVE POS	-	+	+/-
SARS-CoV-2 NEGATIVE	-	-	+
INVALID	-	-	-

See Table 2 to interpret test result statements for the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test.

Table 2. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Results and Interpretation

Result	Interpretation
SARS-CoV-2 POSITIVE	<p>The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) target nucleic acids are detected.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SARS-CoV-2 signal for the N2 nucleic acid target or signals for both nucleic acid targets (N2 and E) have a Ct within the valid range and endpoint above the minimum setting • SPC: NA; SPC is ignored because coronavirus target amplification occurred • Probe Check: PASS; all probe check results pass
SARS-CoV-2 PRESUMPTIVE POS	<p>The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) nucleic acids may be present. Sample should be retested according to the Retest Procedure in Section 17.2. For samples with a repeated presumptive positive result, additional confirmatory testing may be conducted, if it is necessary to differentiate between SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-CoV-1 or other Sarbecovirus currently unknown to infect humans, for epidemiological purposes or clinical management.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SARS-CoV-2 signal for only the E nucleic acid target has a Ct within the valid range and endpoint above the minimum setting • SPC: NA; SPC is ignored because a target amplification has occurred. • Probe Check: PASS; all probe check results pass
SARS-CoV-2 NEGATIVE	<p>The 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) target nucleic acids are not detected.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SARS-CoV-2 signals for two nucleic acid targets (N2 and E) do not have a Ct within the valid range and endpoint above the minimum setting • SPC: PASS; SPC has a Ct within the valid range and endpoint above the minimum setting • Probe Check: PASS; all probe check results pass
INVALID	<p>SPC does not meet acceptance criteria. Presence or absence of the 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) nucleic acids cannot be determined. Repeat test according to the Retest Procedure in Section 17.2.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPC: FAIL; SPC and SARS-CoV-2 signals do not have a Ct within valid range and endpoint below minimum setting

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Probe Check - PASS; all probe check results pass
ERROR	<p>Presence or absence of the 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) nucleic acids cannot be determined. Repeat test according to the Retest Procedure in Section 17.2.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SARS-CoV-2: NO RESULT • SPC: NO RESULT • Probe Check: FAIL¹; all or one of the probe check results fail <p>¹ If the probe check passes, the error is caused by the maximum pressure limit exceeding the acceptable range, no sample added, or by a system component failure.</p>
NO RESULT	<p>Presence or absence of the 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) nucleic acids cannot be determined. Repeat test according to the Retest Procedure in Section 17.2. A NO RESULT indicates that insufficient data were collected. For example, the operator stopped a test that was in progress.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SARS-CoV-2: NO RESULT • SPC: NO RESULT • Probe Check: NA (not applicable)

The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test includes an Early Assay Termination (EAT) function which will provide earlier time to results in high titer specimens if the signal from the target nucleic acid reaches a predetermined threshold before the full 45 PCR cycles have been completed. When SARS-CoV-2 titers are high enough to initiate the EAT function, the SPC amplification curve may not be seen and its results may not be reported.

17 Retests

17.1 Reasons to Repeat the Assay

If any of the test results mentioned below occur, repeat the test once according to instructions in Section 17.2, Retest Procedure.

- A PRESUMPTIVE POS result indicates the 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) nucleic acids may be present. Only one of the SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid target was detected (E gene) while the other SARS-CoV-2 nucleic acid target (N2 gene) was not detected.
 - An INVALID result indicates that the control SPC failed. The sample was not properly processed, PCR is inhibited, or the sample was not properly collected.
 - An ERROR result could be due to, but not limited to, Probe Check Control failure, system component failure, no sample added, or the maximum pressure limits were exceeded.
 - A NO RESULT indicates that insufficient data were collected. For example, cartridge failed integrity test, the operator stopped a test that was in progress, or a power failure occurred.
- If an External Control fails to perform as expected, repeat external control test and/or contact Cepheid for assistance.

17.2 Retest Procedure

To retest a non-determinate result (INVALID, NO RESULT, or ERROR) or a PRESUMPTIVE POS result, use a new cartridge.

Use the leftover sample from the original specimen transport medium tube or new external control tube.

1. Put on a clean pair of gloves. Obtain a new Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge and a new transfer pipette.
2. Check the specimen transport tube or external control tube is closed.
3. Mix the sample by rapidly invert the specimen transport medium tube or external control tube 5 times. Open the cap on the specimen transport tube or external control tube.
4. Open the cartridge lid.
5. Using a clean transfer pipette (supplied), transfer sample (one draw) to the sample chamber with the large opening in the cartridge.
6. Close the cartridge lid.

18 Limitations

- Performance characteristics of this test have been established with the specimen types listed in the Intended Use Section only. The performance of this assay with other specimen types or samples has not been evaluated.
- A false negative result may occur if a specimen is improperly collected, transported or handled. False negative results may also occur if inadequate numbers of organisms are present in the specimen.
- As with any molecular test, mutations within the target regions of Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 could affect primer and/or probe binding resulting in failure to detect the presence of virus.
- This test cannot rule out diseases caused by other bacterial or viral pathogens.

3. Design and manufacturing information (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 3)

This section has been filled out to the best knowledge of the project partners and does not constitute the information which the manufacturer may enter into this section.

No.	Field	Information
3.1	Design Information	<p>The device incorporates sample preparation, nucleic acid extraction and amplification, and detection of the target sequences in specimens using real time PCR assays. Extraction of SARS-CoV-2 is performed using proprietary cell lysis reagents, separation from macromolecules, such as DNA, proteins and lipids and RNA concentration by high salt and ethanol precipitation. Evaluate and optimise extraction method. The following steps were followed for the assay design for the device:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Check the publicly available literature and databases for existing assays for SARS-CoV-2 ○ Choose a target gene ○ Design custom oligonucleotides; forward and reverse primers and fluorescently labelled probes according to appropriate guidelines ISO 20395:2019 ○ Check primer specificity by <i>in silico</i> and wet lab testing ○ Evaluate primer and probe properties by <i>in silico</i> analysis: melting temperature (T_m), secondary structure, and complementarity

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Validate the primers and/or probes and optimise the protocol <p>Validation tests of the production units of the device performed to ensure it can operate within its specifications in near patient settings. At every stage the design is validated against similar technologies which incorporate nucleic acid extraction and real time PCR detection.</p>
3.2	Manufacturing Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Cartridge and extraction reagent manufacture ○ Oligonucleotides synthesis and purification by third party supplier (appropriate certificate attached) ○ QC of cartridges, extraction reagents and oligonucleotides ○ Dilution of reagents and preparation of batches to starting concentrations ○ Assembly of devices incorporating all elements e.g. loading cartridges ○ QC of batches ○ Packaging and final packaging

4. General Safety and Performance Requirements (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 4)

CE Declaration of Conformity

Manufacturer:

Cepheid
904 Caribbean Drive
Sunnyvale, CA 94089-1189

The Cepheid Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2 catalog # XPRSARS-COV2-10 has been tested to the requirements of the following directives and standards. We, the undersigned, hereby declare that the device specified above conforms to the stated directives and standards as applicable.

IVDR

XXX

XXX

In addition the above product has been manufactured under a certified Quality system compliant with the following standards, granted by XXX Notified Body:

ISO 13485

_Regulatory Officer_____

Sign

Stamp

Date

10.1 General

- For in vitro diagnostic use.
- Positive results are indicative of presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA.
- Report all positive results to the appropriate health authorities as required.
- Treat all biological specimens, including used cartridges, as if capable of transmitting infectious agents. Because it is often impossible to know which might be infectious, all biological specimens should be handled using standard precautions. Guidelines for specimen handling are available from the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute.
- Follow safety procedures set by your institution for working with chemicals and handling biological specimens.
- Consult your institution's environmental waste personnel on proper disposal of used cartridges, which may contain amplified material. This material may exhibit characteristics of federal EPA Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) hazardous waste requiring specific disposal requirements. Check state and local regulations as they may differ from federal disposal regulations. Institutions should check the hazardous waste disposal requirements within their respective countries.

10.2 Specimens

- Maintain proper storage conditions during specimen transport to ensure the integrity of the specimen (see Section 12, Specimen Collection, Transport, and Storage). Specimen stability under shipping conditions other than those recommended has not been evaluated.

10.3 Assay/Reagent

- Do not open the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge lid except when adding specimen.
- Do not use a cartridge that has been dropped after removing it from the packaging.
- Do not shake the cartridge. Shaking or dropping the cartridge after opening the cartridge lid may yield non-determinate results.
- Do not place the sample ID label on the cartridge lid or on the barcode label on the cartridge.
- Do not use a cartridge with a damaged barcode label.
- Do not use a cartridge that has a damaged reaction tube.
- Each single-use Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridge is used to process one test. Do not reuse processed cartridges.
- Each single-use disposable pipette is used to transfer one specimen. Do not reuse disposable pipettes
- Do not use a cartridge if it appears wet or if the lid seal appears to have been broken.
- Wear clean lab coats and gloves. Change gloves between the handling of each specimen.
- In the event of a spill of specimens or controls, wear gloves and absorb the spill with paper towels. Then, thoroughly clean the contaminated area with a 10% freshly prepared household chlorine bleach. Allow a minimum of two minutes of contact time. Ensure the work area is dry before using 70% denatured ethanol to remove bleach residue. Allow surface to dry completely before proceeding. Or, follow your institution's standard procedures for a contamination or spill event. For equipment, follow the manufacturer's recommendations for decontamination of equipment.
- Biological specimens, transfer devices, and used cartridges should be considered capable of transmitting infectious agents requiring standard precautions. Follow your institution's environmental waste procedures for proper disposal of used cartridges and unused reagents. These materials may exhibit characteristics of chemical hazardous waste requiring specific disposal. If country or regional regulations do not provide clear direction on proper disposal, biological specimens and used cartridges should be disposed per WHO [World Health Organization] medical waste handling and disposal guidelines.

11 Chemical Hazards

- Signal Word: WARNING
- UN GHS Hazard Statements
 - Harmful if swallowed.
 - May be harmful in contact with skin.
 - Causes eye irritation.
- UN GHS Precautionary Statements
 - Prevention
 - Wash hands thoroughly after handling.
 - Response
 - Call a POISON CENTER or doctor/physician if you feel unwell.
 - If skin irritation occurs: Get medical advice/attention.
 - IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing.
 - If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.

5. Benefit-Risk Analysis and Risk Management (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 5)

No.	Field	Information
5	Risk Management Plan and Report	<p>Risk management plan for Cepheid Xpert® Xpress SARS-CoV-2 catalog # XPRSARS-COV2-10</p> <p>Define scope: define product</p> <p>Intended use: The Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test is a real-time RT-PCR test intended for the qualitative detection of nucleic acid from the SARS-CoV-2 in nasopharyngeal swab, nasal swab, or nasal wash/aspirate specimen collected from individuals who are suspected of COVID-19 infection.</p> <p>Risk Management activities throughout the product life cycle</p> <p>Identify the risk management team as to who will prepare and approve documentation.</p> <p>Criteria for the acceptability of the risk relating to the product.</p> <p>Method to identify and reduce the risk by describing risk control procedures.</p> <p>Describe how post production information will be gathered and incorporated into the activities relating to the risk management for the product.</p>
5.1	Specific Usability Risks (only for Self-Testing / Near-Patient Testing)	<p>Personal protective equipment that is donned for sample collection should continue to be worn when performing the test and dispose of all contaminated material. Decontaminate surfaces and equipment between each patient sample</p>

6. Benefit-Risk Analysis and Risk Management (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6)

No.	Field	Information
6.1	Specimen Type / Handling	<p>nasopharyngeal swab or nasal wash/aspirate</p> <p>Nasopharyngeal swab, nasal swab and nasal wash/aspirate specimens can be stored in viral transport medium or saline, at room temperature (15-30 °C) for up to 8 hours and refrigerated (2-</p>

		8 °C) up to 7 days until testing is performed on the GeneXpert Instrument Systems.																																																												
6.2	Analytical Performance	<p>Analytical Performance</p> <p>Analytical Sensitivity (Limit of Detection)</p> <p>Studies were performed to determine the analytical limit of detection (LoD) of the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2. The LoD of Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 was established using one lot of reagent and limiting dilutions of live SARS-CoV-2 virus (USA_WA1/2020) prepared in viral transport medium and NP swab clinical matrix. The concentration level with observed hit rates greater than or equal to 95% in the LoD determination study were 0.0050 and 0.0200 PFU/mL for the N2 target and E target, respectively (Table 4). Verification of the estimated LoD claim was performed on one reagent lot in replicates of 20 prepared in pooled NP swab clinical matrix. The LoD is the lowest concentration (reported as PFU/mL) of live SARS-CoV-2 virus samples that can be reproducibly distinguished from negative samples 95% of the time with 95% confidence. The claimed LoD is 0.0200 PFU/mL (Table 4).</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table 4. LoD Determination using USA-WA1/2020 Strain</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Strain</th> <th rowspan="2">Concentration (PFU/mL)</th> <th rowspan="2">Total Valid Results</th> <th colspan="2">Hit Rate (%)</th> <th colspan="2">Mean Ct</th> </tr> <tr> <th>N2 Target</th> <th>E Target</th> <th>N2 Target</th> <th>E Target</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="8">SARS-CoV-2 virus (USA_WA1/2020)</td> <td>0.0200</td> <td>20</td> <td>100</td> <td>95.0</td> <td>38.3</td> <td>36.4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0050</td> <td>22</td> <td>95.5</td> <td>68.2</td> <td>40.5</td> <td>39.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0025</td> <td>22</td> <td>90.9</td> <td>36.4</td> <td>41.5</td> <td>39.6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0010</td> <td>22</td> <td>50.0</td> <td>18.2</td> <td>42.0</td> <td>42.0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0005</td> <td>22</td> <td>45.5</td> <td>18.2</td> <td>41.7</td> <td>41.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0003</td> <td>22</td> <td>18.2</td> <td>4.5</td> <td>42.1</td> <td>44.9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0.0001</td> <td>22</td> <td>9.1</td> <td>0</td> <td>42.9</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> <td>N/A</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Analytical Reactivity (Inclusivity)</p> <p>The inclusivity of Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 was evaluated using in silico analysis of the assay primers and probes in relation to 36,863 SARS-CoV-2 sequences available in the GISAID gene database for two targets, E and N2.</p> <p>For the E target, 142 matching sequences were excluded due to ambiguity codes, which reduced the total to 36,721 sequences. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 had 99.4% match to the sequences with the exception of 187 sequences that had a single mismatch and 18 sequences with additional mismatches. Of the 18 sequences with additional mismatches, one sequence contained 2 mismatches in the forward primer region, three sequences contained a 5 nucleotide gap, 2 sequences contained multiple mismatches at the 3' end of the amplicon, and twelve sequences contained a 'AA' dinucleotide but this lies between the oligonucleotides used in the assay. None of these mismatches are expected to affect the performance of the assay.</p> <p>For the N2 target, 132 matching sequences were excluded due to ambiguity codes, which reduced the total to 36,731</p>	Strain	Concentration (PFU/mL)	Total Valid Results	Hit Rate (%)		Mean Ct		N2 Target	E Target	N2 Target	E Target	SARS-CoV-2 virus (USA_WA1/2020)	0.0200	20	100	95.0	38.3	36.4	0.0050	22	95.5	68.2	40.5	39.1	0.0025	22	90.9	36.4	41.5	39.6	0.0010	22	50.0	18.2	42.0	42.0	0.0005	22	45.5	18.2	41.7	41.5	0.0003	22	18.2	4.5	42.1	44.9	0.0001	22	9.1	0	42.9	N/A	0	0	0	0	N/A	N/A
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		<p>sequences. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 had 98.9% match to the sequences with the exception of 262 sequences that had a single mismatch and one sequence contained 3 mismatches. None of these mismatches are predicted to have a negative impact on the performance of the assay.</p>																															
<p>6.3</p>	<p>Clinical Performance</p>	<p>Clinical Evaluation</p> <p>The performance of the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test was evaluated using archived clinical nasopharyngeal (NP) swab specimens in viral transport medium. A total of 45 SARS-CoV-2 positive and 45 SARS-CoV-2 negative NP swab specimens were tested with Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 in a randomized and blinded fashion.</p> <p>All the 45 SARS-CoV-2 positive specimens and 30 of the 45 SARS-CoV-2 negative specimens were collected during COVID-19 pandemic in the US and had previously been characterized as positive or negative for SARS-CoV-2 by an EUA RT-PCR test.</p> <p>Fifteen of the 45 SARS-CoV-2 negative NP swab specimens were collected before December 2019 and are expected to be negative for SARS-CoV-2.</p> <p>Positive Percent Agreement (PPA) and Negative Percent Agreement (NPA) were determined by comparing the results of the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test relative to the expected results. Results of these 90 archived clinical NP swab specimens are shown in Table 3. The PPA was 97.8% (95% CI: 88.4% - 99.6%) and the NPA was 95.6% (95% CI: 85.2% - 98.8%).</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Table 3. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Performance Results</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="595 1272 1347 1451"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2" rowspan="2"></th> <th colspan="3">Expected Results</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Positive</th> <th>Negative</th> <th>Total</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="3">Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2</td> <td>Positive</td> <td>44^a</td> <td>2^b</td> <td>46</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Negative</td> <td>1</td> <td>43</td> <td>44</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Total</td> <td>45</td> <td>45</td> <td>90</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">PPA</td> <td colspan="3">97.8% (95% CI: 88.4% - 99.6%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">NPA</td> <td colspan="3">95.6% (95% CI: 85.2% - 98.8%)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>a. One specimen was reported as "SARS-CoV-2 Presumptive Pos" in initial testing and yielded a "SARS-CoV-2 Positive" test result upon retesting.</p> <p>b. The two false positive specimens were collected during the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p>Analytical Specificity (Exclusivity)</p> <p>An in silico analysis for possible cross-reactions with all the organisms listed in Table 5 was conducted by mapping primers and probes in the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test individually to the sequences downloaded from the GISAID database. E primers and probes are not specific for SARS-CoV-2 and will detect Human and Bat SARS-coronavirus. No potential unintended cross reactivity with other organisms listed in Table 5 is expected based on the in silico analysis.</p>			Expected Results			Positive	Negative	Total	Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2	Positive	44 ^a	2 ^b	46	Negative	1	43	44	Total	45	45	90	PPA		97.8% (95% CI: 88.4% - 99.6%)			NPA		95.6% (95% CI: 85.2% - 98.8%)		
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Table 5. Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 Analytical Specificity Microorganisms

Microorganisms from the Same Genetic Family	High Priority Organisms
Human coronavirus 229E	Adenovirus (e.g. C1 Ad. 71)
Human coronavirus OC43	Human Metapneumovirus (hMPV)
Human coronavirus HKU1	Parainfluenza virus 1-4
Human coronavirus NL63	Influenza A
SARS-coronavirus	Influenza B
MERS-coronavirus	Influenza C
Bat coronavirus	Enterovirus (e.g. EV68)
	Respiratory syncytial virus
	Rhinovirus
	<i>Chlamydia pneumoniae</i>
	<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>
	<i>Legionella pneumophila</i>
	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>
	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
	<i>Bordetella pertussis</i>
	<i>Mycoplasma pneumoniae</i>
	<i>Pneumocystis jirovecii</i> (PJP)
	<i>Parvovirus</i>
	<i>Candida albicans</i>
	<i>Corynebacterium diphtheriae</i>
	<i>Legionella non-pneumophila</i>
	<i>Bacillus anthracis</i> (Anthrax)
	<i>Moraxella catarrhalis</i>
	<i>Neisseria elongata and meningitidis</i>
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
	<i>Staphylococcus salivarius</i>
	<i>Leptospira</i>
	<i>Chlamydia psittaci</i>
	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i> (Q-Fever)
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Reproducibility

The reproducibility of the Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 test was established at three sites using a 5-member panel including one negative sample, two low positive (~1.5x LoD) and two moderate positive (~3x LoD) samples. The negative sample consisted of simulated matrix without target microorganism or target RNA. The positive samples were contrived samples in a simulated matrix using either AccuPlex SARS-CoV-2 reference material (targeting the N2 and E genes) or inactivated SARS-CoV Urbani strain (targeting the E gene). Testing was conducted over six (6) days, using three (3) lots of Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2 cartridges at three (3) participating sites each with two (2) operators to yield a total of 144 observations per panel member (3 Sites x 2 Operators x 3 Lots x 2 Days/Lot x 2 Runs x 2 Reps = 144 observations/panel member). The results from the study are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of Reproducibility Results - % Agreement by Study Site/Operator

Sample	Site 1			Site 2			Site 3			% Total Agreement ^a by Sample
	Op1	Op2	Site	Op1	Op2	Site	Op1	Op2	Site	
Negative	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (144/144)
SARS-CoV-2 Low Pos	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	95.8% (23/24)	97.9% (47/48)	95.8% (23/24)	100% (24/24)	97.9% (47/48)	98.6% (142/144)
SARS-CoV-2 Mod Pos	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (144/144)
SARS-CoV Low Pos	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (144/144)
SARS-CoV Mod Pos	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (24/24)	100% (24/24)	100% (48/48)	100% (144/144)

a. Agreement was calculated as the percentage of observed results that were in agreement with the expected results.

6.4	Performance of self-testing devices / Near-patient testing devices	
6.5	Scientific Validity	<p>Positive Percent Agreement 97.8% (95% CI: 88.4%–99.6%)</p> <p>Negative Percent Agreement Clinical Evaluation 95.6% (95% CI: 85.2%–98.8%)</p> <p>Testing performed with 45 positives and 45 negatives</p>
6.6	Performance Evaluation Report	
6.7	Stability (REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.3)	<p>Section 10: Stability and Reactivity</p> <p>10.1 Reactivity No dangerous reaction known under conditions of normal use.</p> <p>10.2 Chemical stability Stable</p> <p>10.3 Possibility of hazardous reactions Hazardous polymerization will not occur.</p> <p>10.4 Conditions to avoid Incompatible materials. Burning plastic cartridge containing reagents may liberate toxic byproducts</p> <p>10.5 Incompatible materials Acids.</p> <p>10.6 Hazardous decomposition products Burning plastic cartridge containing reagents may liberate toxic byproducts.</p>
6.8	Software Verification and Validation / Functional Safety / Cybersecurity	

	(REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.4)																																																																									
6.9	CHEMICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES (REGULATION (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Annex II Section 6.5)	<p>Section 9: Physical and Chemical Properties</p> <p>9.1 Information on Physical and Chemical Properties</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="596 450 1355 736"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="4">Material Description</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Physical Form</td> <td>Liquid</td> <td>Color</td> <td>Colorless</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Odor</td> <td>Odorless</td> <td>Odor Threshold</td> <td>Data lacking</td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="4">General Properties</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Boiling Point</td> <td>212 °F(100 °C)</td> <td>Melting Point/Freezing Point</td> <td>32 °F(0 °C)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Decomposition Temperature</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td>pH</td> <td>3.3 to 8.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Specific Gravity/Relative Density</td> <td>= 1 Water=1</td> <td>Water Solubility</td> <td>Soluble 100 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Viscosity</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td>Explosive Properties</td> <td>Data lacking</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Oxidizing Properties:</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="4">Volatility</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Vapor Pressure</td> <td>Minimal</td> <td>Vapor Density</td> <td>Data lacking</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Evaporation Rate</td> <td>Minimal</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="4">Flammability</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Flash Point</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td>UEL</td> <td>Data lacking</td> </tr> <tr> <td>L.E.L.</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td>Autoignition</td> <td>Data lacking</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Flammability (solid, gas)</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="4">Environmental</th> </tr> <tr> <td>Octanol/Water Partition Coefficient</td> <td>Data lacking</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>9.2 Other Information No additional physical and chemical parameters noted.</p>	Material Description				Physical Form	Liquid	Color	Colorless	Odor	Odorless	Odor Threshold	Data lacking	General Properties				Boiling Point	212 °F(100 °C)	Melting Point/Freezing Point	32 °F(0 °C)	Decomposition Temperature	Data lacking	pH	3.3 to 8.8	Specific Gravity/Relative Density	= 1 Water=1	Water Solubility	Soluble 100 %	Viscosity	Data lacking	Explosive Properties	Data lacking	Oxidizing Properties:	Data lacking			Volatility				Vapor Pressure	Minimal	Vapor Density	Data lacking	Evaporation Rate	Minimal			Flammability				Flash Point	Data lacking	UEL	Data lacking	L.E.L.	Data lacking	Autoignition	Data lacking	Flammability (solid, gas)	Data lacking			Environmental				Octanol/Water Partition Coefficient	Data lacking		
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6.9.1	Nanoparticle Technology	N/A																																																																								
6.9.2	Hazardous Substances	<p>Safety Data Sheet Effective Date: January 2023 Supersedes Date: August 2022</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Xpert Flu/RSV XC; Xpert Xpress Flu; Xpert Xpress Flu/RSV Xpert Flu; Xpert Xpress SARS-COV-2 Xpert Xpress SARS-CoV-2/Flu/RSV Xpert Xpress CoV-2 plus Xpert Mpx</i></p> <p>Section 2: Hazards Identification</p> <p>EU/EEC According to: Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP)/REACH 1907/2006 [amended by 453/2010]</p> <p>2.1 Classification of the Substance or Mixture CLP The following SDS is for the final finished mixture product only as used in the laboratory. The product contains beads and reagents in the cartridge or in off-board containers. Exemptions for disclosing some component information are pursuant to CLP Article 1(5)(d) and 29 CFR 1910.1200(g)(2)(i)(C)(1)&(2). Not classified</p> <p>2.2 Label Elements CLP Hazard Statements No label element(s) required</p> <p>2.3 Other Hazards CLP According to Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 (CLP) this material is not considered hazardous.</p> <p>UN GHS (Labeling Content Used on Products) According to: UN Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS)</p> <p>2.1 Classification of the Substance or Mixture UN GHS Acute Toxicity Oral 5 Skin Mild Irritation 3 Eye Mild Irritation 2B</p> <p>2.2 Label Elements UN GHS WARNING</p> <p>Hazard statements Harmful if swallowed May be harmful in contact with skin Causes eye irritation</p> <p>Precautionary statements Prevention Wash hands thoroughly after handling. Response If skin irritation occurs: Get medical advice/attention. IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing. If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention. Call a POISON CENTER or doctor/physician if you feel unwell.</p> <p>2.3 Other Hazards UN GHS According to the Globally Harmonized System for Classification and Labeling (GHS) this product is considered hazardous.</p>																																																																								

		<p>United States (US) According to: OSHA 29 CFR 1910.1200 HCS</p> <p>2.1 Classification of the Substance or Mixture OSHA HCS 2012 Eye Mild Irritation 2B</p> <p>2.2 Label Elements OSHA HCS 2012</p> <p>Hazard statements Harmful if swallowed May be harmful in contact with skin Causes eye irritation</p> <p>Precautionary statements</p> <p>Prevention Wash hands thoroughly after handling.</p> <p>Response IF IN EYES: Rinse cautiously with water for several minutes. Remove contact lenses, if present and easy to do. Continue rinsing. If eye irritation persists: Get medical advice/attention.</p> <p>2.3 Other Hazards OSHA HCS 2012 Under United States Regulations (29 CFR 1910.1200 - Hazard Communication Standard), this product is not considered hazardous.</p> <hr/> <p>Canada According to: WHMIS</p> <p>2.1 Classification of the Substance or Mixture WHMIS Not classified</p> <p>2.2 Label Elements WHMIS No label element(s) required.</p> <p>2.3 Other Hazards WHMIS In Canada, the product mentioned above is not considered hazardous under the Workplace Hazardous Materials Information System (WHMIS).</p> <hr/> <p>2.4 Other Information All other reagents, beads, and other constituents are at concentrations less than 1% in the mixture or not considered hazardous under US hazard communication regulations (29 CFR 1910.1200), EU directives for classification and labeling of substances or mixtures or the Global Harmonization System for classification and labeling of substances or mixtures.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Αρτη Μίση</i></p> <p>Section 3: Composition/Information on Ingredients</p> <p>3.1 Substances Material does not meet the criteria of a substance.</p> <p>3.2 Mixtures</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="603 1151 1315 1218"> <thead> <tr> <th rowspan="2">Chemical Name</th> <th rowspan="2">Identifiers</th> <th rowspan="2">%</th> <th rowspan="2">LD50/LC50</th> <th colspan="2">Composition</th> </tr> <tr> <th>Classifications According to Regulation/Directive</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Guanidine Thiocyanate</td> <td>CAS: 593-84-0 EINECS: 209-812-1</td> <td>10% - 20%</td> <td>593 mg/kg</td> <td>EU CLP: Acute Tox. 5, H302, H313, H320 UN GHS: Acute Tox. 5 (Orl); Skin Irrit. 3; Eye Irrit. 2B OSHA HCS 2012: Acute Tox. 5 (Orl); Eye Irrit. 2B</td> <td>NDA</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Chemical Name	Identifiers	%	LD50/LC50	Composition		Classifications According to Regulation/Directive	Comments	Guanidine Thiocyanate	CAS: 593-84-0 EINECS: 209-812-1	10% - 20%	593 mg/kg	EU CLP: Acute Tox. 5, H302, H313, H320 UN GHS: Acute Tox. 5 (Orl); Skin Irrit. 3; Eye Irrit. 2B OSHA HCS 2012: Acute Tox. 5 (Orl); Eye Irrit. 2B	NDA
Chemical Name	Identifiers	%					LD50/LC50	Composition								
			Classifications According to Regulation/Directive	Comments												
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6.9.3	Substances of Animal / Human / Microbiological Origin	The bovine serum albumin (BSA) in the beads within this product was produced and manufactured exclusively from bovine plasma sourced in the United States. No ruminant protein or other animal protein was fed to the animals; the animals passed ante- and postmortem testing. During processing, there was no mixing of the material with other animal materials.														
6.9.4	Sterile Devices or Devices with Defined Microbiological Condition															
6.9.5	Constructional Safety															
6.9.5.1	Mechanical Safety															
6.9.5.2	Electrical safety / electromagnetic compatibility															

6.9.5.3	Ionising and non-ionising radiation	
6.9.5.4	Environmental protection and safe disposal	<p>13.1 Waste treatment methods</p> <p>Product waste</p> <p>Dispose of content and/or container in accordance with local, regional, national, and/or international regulations.</p> <p>Packaging waste Dispose of content and/or container in accordance with local, regional, national, and/or international regulations.</p> <p>13.2 Other Information</p> <p>Biological specimens, transfer devices, and used cartridges should be considered capable of transmitting infectious agents requiring standard precautions. Follow your institution's environmental waste procedures for proper disposal of used cartridges and unused reagents. These materials may exhibit characteristics of chemical hazardous waste requiring specific national or regional disposal procedures. If national or regional regulations do not provide clear direction on proper disposal, biological specimens and used cartridges should be disposed per WHO (World Health Organization) medical waste handling and disposal guidelines</p>
6.9.5.5	Packaging	
6.9.5.6	Devices with connection to other device(s)	N/A
6.9.6	Devices with a Measuring Function	N/A

7. Summary of Safety and Performance (SSP) (only class C and D devices) (Regulation (EU) 2017/746 (IVDR), Article 29)

Note: This section to include information such as name of device, use, description, performance evaluation, reference to harmonised standards, suggestions as to training required for users, any warnings and precautions about its use.

Appendix C: Examples of how to fulfil analytical performance categories.

Analytical performance category	<p>*ISO 20395:2019 (qPCR and dPCR) suggested experiment design ** Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. Evaluation of precision of quantitative measurement procedures; Approved Guideline – Third Edition. CLSI EP05-A3.</p>
Clinical sensitivity	<p>A dilution series of template prepared using suitable materials. These materials could be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - available reference materials - materials derived from specimens which contain the analyte <p>Materials to be tested to include different types/strains of analyte and include suitable matrix.</p>
Analytical and clinical specificity	<p><i>In silico</i> and wet laboratory testing the role of interfering substances such as human DNA, closely related species and wider common human pathogens. Negative controls to be selected which reflect samples from the intended target population where the device is to be used.</p>
Accuracy, trueness (bias)	<p>Accuracy is the deviation of a single measurement result compared to an available reference measurement value or the nominal value of an accepted reference material. Trueness is the deviation remaining after averaging a large number of replicate measurements. Trueness can be an estimate for the systematic measurement error (bias)</p>
<p>Precision</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repeatability • Reproducibility 	<p>Repeatability/within-run precision performed testing at least two different concentrations in at minimum duplicate replication in one run by single operator.</p> <p>Within-laboratory precision to be measured testing at least two different concentrations with two replicates over twenty days, performing two runs each day**.</p> <p>Reproducibility tested under the changing of conditions, by different operators, laboratories to be performed at three sites on five days**.</p>
LOD	<p>The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration that allows detection of the presence of target nucleic acid with acceptable probability; it is not required to quantify the nucleic acid concentration at LOD. The acceptable probability and the LOD value are defined in the assay's product design specifications. Typically, a detection probability of 95% is required at LOD. Normally an approximate value for LOD is sufficient for assay validation. Determination of LOD by measurement involves a dilution series covering the expected LOD while applying a sufficiently high number of replicate measurements. Regulatory bodies can have specific requirements for verification of the claimed LOD for an approved assay (e.g.</p>

	usage of 100 replicates). Note that sometimes LOD is referred to as analytical sensitivity.
LOQ	The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest level of nucleic acid concentration that can be determined with acceptable performance. The acceptable performance and the value of LOQ are defined in the assay's product design specifications. Typically, a relative uncertainty of 20% is required for the measurement of precision. The relative uncertainty of the precision can be estimated from $\sqrt{1/2 \cdot (N - 1)}$ where N is the number of replicate measurements. For example, a minimum of 10 replicates* at LOQ would result in a precision of (20 ± 5) %. The assay performance shall be evaluated at different concentration levels close to LOQ. Concentration increment should be maximum twofold.
Linearity	Proportionality between instrument response and quantity of nucleic acid target sequence. The linear range should be defined in the assay's product design specifications, and validated This should include a range of template concentrations, e.g. small increments in dilutions to cover a range of λ values.
Cut-off value	Quantity value (e.g. nucleic acid concentration) selected to determine clinical sensitivity and clinical specificity. The cut-off value is used as limit to identify presence or absence of a specific disease or condition.
Specimen handling	General guidance for handling specimens for nucleic acid detection is given in ISO 17822:2020 and ISO 20395:2019. Potentially infectious specimens should be handled with care (https://www.who.int/activities/strengthening-public-health-laboratory-services/videos)
Cross-reactivity	Evaluate the potential of interfering substances which may be present in the sample. For example organisms which share sequence homology, microorganisms concurrently present in specimens of healthy subjects, and relevant co-infections should be considered.